

Study of the Liver Function Tests' Predictive Value in the Early Diagnosis of Prediabetes at DMCH**Chandra Mauleshwar Jha¹, Bharat Kumar², Vijay Kumar Singh³, Sheela Kumari⁴, Devanand Kumar⁵, Rishikesh Kumar⁶**^{1,5,6}Junior Resident, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India²Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India³Professor, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India⁴Professor & HOD, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India

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Abstract:**Background:** The early detection of prediabetes is crucial in preventing the progression of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Liver function tests (LFTs), which include measures of enzymes like alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST), have been increasingly recognized for their potential role in identifying metabolic disturbances associated with insulin resistance and prediabetes. This study explores the utility of LFTs in predicting prediabetes, potentially offering a simple, cost-effective screening tool for at-risk populations at DMCH.**Method:** The study conducted a cross-sectional analysis of patients attending the DMCH. We recruited people between the ages of 20 and 65 into two groups: 30 healthy individuals with normal blood sugar levels (normoglycemia) and 30 individuals with prediabetes. We compared liver function test (LFT) parameters across these groups. Statistical tests were employed for the analysis in this study.**Result:** Results revealed that ALT median was significantly increased in prediabetes compared to normoglycemia (19.5 vs. 13.8 IU/L, respectively; $p = 0.002$). For AST, there were no significant differences between the two groups investigated ($p = 0.231$). In the case of ALP, significantly increased medians were observed in prediabetes compared to normoglycemia (90.7 and 73.1 IU/L, respectively; $p = 0.005$). ROC curve analysis revealed that ALT (AUC = 0.891; 95% CI = 0.688 - 0.894; $p = 0.001$; cut-off value = 16.1IU/L; sensitivity = 72.4%; specificity = 73.3%) and ALP (AUC = 0.824; 95% CI = 0.621 - 0.828; $p = 0.001$; cut-off value = 80.2 IU/L; sensitivity = 67.2%; specificity = 66.7%) were good predictors in differentiating between prediabetes and normoglycemia.**Conclusion:** This research concludes that ALT and ALP are effective predictors of prediabetes, but further research is needed to fully comprehend the mechanism underlying the link between liver function enzymes and diabetes risk.**Keywords:** Prediabetes, Diabetes, Liver function enzymes, Body mass index.

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Introduction

Prediabetes is a crucial stage in the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), characterized by blood glucose levels higher than normal but not yet in the diabetic range. Identifying individuals at this stage is crucial for early intervention and preventing the progression to T2DM. Traditional diagnostic markers for prediabetes include fasting blood glucose (FBG) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c). However, these markers may not detect all individuals at risk. Recent studies have indicated that liver function tests (LFTs) might offer

additional predictive value for identifying prediabetes, given the liver's role in glucose metabolism and insulin resistance. [1,2] The liver is pivotal in maintaining glucose balance through gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis. Insulin resistance, a hallmark of prediabetes, often leads to hepatic steatosis, which can cause elevations in liver enzymes like ALT and AST. [2] These enzymes are commonly measured in LFTs and have been associated with metabolic syndrome components. Several studies have explored the

relationship between liver enzymes and prediabetes. [3-5] Elevated ALT levels have been consistently linked to insulin resistance and the development of T2DM. Although less specific to the liver, AST also correlates with metabolic disturbances. Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), another liver enzyme, has been shown to predict the onset of diabetes, suggesting that LFTs might be useful in early detection strategies. [5,6] given the rising prevalence of T2DM globally, there is a pressing need for early detection strategies that go beyond traditional glucose-based markers. The liver plays a central role in glucose homeostasis and insulin sensitivity, suggesting that liver enzymes could be early indicators of metabolic disturbances leading to prediabetes. This study explores the utility of LFTs in predicting prediabetes, potentially offering a simple, cost-effective screening tool for at-risk populations at DMCH.

Material and Methods

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional analysis of individuals without a prior diagnosis of diabetes, conducted at the Department of Physiology of DMC, Laheriasarai, and Darbhanga, India (May 2024 to August 2024). The study population includes 60 adults aged 20-65 years in two groups of people. The first group included 30 healthy individuals (Normoglycemia), and the second group included 30 prediabetics. The definition of normoglycemia, prediabetes, and diabetes was due to the American Diabetes Association (ADA) criteria, which are based on assessing fasting blood glucose (FBG: Less than 100, 100-125, and ≥ 126 mg/dL, respectively) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c: Less than 5.7, 5.7-6.4 and $\geq 6.5\%$, respectively).⁷ Only people who met these criteria were included. Patients with cholecystitis, alcoholic liver diseases, and hepatitis B and C viral infections were excluded from the research when they were diagnosed with the virus.

Patients under medication (hepatotoxic and anti-tuberculosis drugs), unwilling to participate in the study, or who had liver diseases were also excluded. Besides, pregnant women with gestational diabetes were also excluded.

Data Collection and Laboratory Analysis:

Participants underwent detailed clinical assessments, including a thorough medical history and physical examination. Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast of up to 8 hrs to measure FPG, HbA1c, and LFTs (ALT, AST, ALP). The results were analyzed to identify correlations between LFT parameters and glycemic indices.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS software. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm SD, and categorical variables as percentages. Pearson correlation coefficients were used to assess the relationship between LFTs and glycemic indices. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were constructed to evaluate the predictive value of LFTs for prediabetes, with sensitivity, specificity, and area under the curve (AUC) calculated.

Results

In Table 1, the BMI of individuals with prediabetes was significantly higher than those with normal blood sugar levels (28.4 ± 2.9 vs. 26.1 ± 1.4 kg/m², respectively; $p = 0.003$). The prevalence of obesity was higher among prediabetes with 60% of individuals in these groups being fat. In contrast, obesity accounted for only 16.67% of cases in individuals with normal blood sugar levels (normoglycemia).

The FBG and HbA1c evaluations aligned with the criteria set by the ADA. The values for normoglycemia and prediabetes were as follows: 83.2 ± 2.6 mg/dL and $4.2 \pm 1.3\%$, and 111.8 ± 1.9 mg/dL and $6.7 \pm 1.8\%$, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline properties of normoglycemia and prediabetes,

Characteristic	Mean \pm SD or Number (%)		p-value
	Normoglycemia (N = 30)	Prediabetes (N = 30)	
Age (years)	39.4 ± 1.1	41.6 ± 1.4	0.071
Age group (years)			
< 30	6 (20%)	5 (16.67%)	0.214
31-50	15 (50%)	18 (60%)	
> 50	9 (30%)	7 (23.33%)	
Gender			
Male	17 (56.67%)	19 (63.33%)	0.613
Female	13 (43.33%)	11 (36.67%)	
Height (cm)	163.1 ± 2.1	164.8 ± 2.2	0.673
Weight (kg)	72.1 ± 1.01	85.4 ± 2.1	0.002
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.1 ± 1.4	28.4 ± 2.9	0.003
BMI groups			
Normal	16 (53.33%)	2 (6.67%)	0.001
Overweight	9 (30%)	10(33.33%)	

Obese	5 (16.67%)	18(60%)	
Waist (cm)	85.3 ± 5.3	89.8 ± 4.5	0.002
FBG mg/dL	83.2 ± 2.6	111.8 ± 1.9	0.001
HbA1c (%)	4.2 ± 1.3	6.7 ± 1.8	0.021
p: Mann-Whitney U test (significant p-value is indicated in bold)			

The evaluation of liver function tests showed that the median value of ALT was significantly higher in individuals with prediabetes compared to those with normoglycemia (19.5 vs. 13.8 IU/L, respectively; p = 0.002). The analysis of variance (ANOVA) for AST revealed no statistically

significant differences among the two groups examined (p = 0.231). The study found that ALP levels were considerably higher in individuals with prediabetes than those with normal blood sugar levels (90.7 and 73.1 IU/L, respectively; p = 0.005) shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Median levels of ALT, AST, and ALP in serum of normoglycemia and prediabetes

Variable	Median (IQR: 25-75%)		p-value
	Normoglycemia (N =30)	Prediabetes (N = 30)	
ALT (IU/L)	13.8 (10.5-17.1)	19.5 (14.9-35.0)	0.002
AST (IU/L)	16.5 (12.9-26.0)	18.6 (13.3-28.9)	0.231
ALP (IU/L)	73.1 (64.5-85.1)	90.7 (73.9-112.6)	0.005

ALT: Alanine aminotransferase; AST: Aspartate aminotransferase; ALP: Alkaline phosphatase; IQR: Interquartile range; p: Kruskal-Wallis's test probability (significant p-value is indicated in bold)

ROC curve analysis demonstrated that ALT and ALP were effective predictors for distinguishing between prediabetes and normoglycemia. ALT had an AUC of 0.891 (95% CI = 0.688 - 0.894, p = 0.001) with a cut-off value of 16.1 IU/L, sensitivity of 72.4%, and specificity of 73.3%. ALP had an

AUC of 0.824 (95% CI = 0.621 - 0.828, p = 0.001) with a cut-off value of 80.2 IU/L, sensitivity of 67.2%, and specificity of 66.7%. Both factors in diabetes did not demonstrate predictive ability, and there was no substantial power to differentiate between them (Table 3 and Figure 1).

Figure 1: Receiver-operator curve analysis (ROC)

Table 3: Receiver-operator curve (ROC) analysis of ALT AST and ALP in prediabetes

Variable	AUC	95% CI	p-value	Cut-off value (IU/L)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Prediabetes						
ALT	0.891	0.688 - 0.894	0.002	16.1	72.4	73.3
AST	0.673	0.448 - 0.699	0.162	18.7	55.2	53.3
ALP	0.824	0.621 - 0.828	0.002	80.2	67.2	66.7

ALT: Alanine aminotransferase; AST: Aspartate aminotransferase; ALP: Alkaline phosphatase; AUC: Area under curve; CI: Confidence interval; p: Probability (significant p-value is indicated in bold).

Discussion

Insulin resistance and beta β -cell malfunction coexist in persons with prediabetes, occurring before any observable alterations in blood glucose levels. Research has indicated that those with prediabetes have a higher likelihood of developing early-stage nephropathy, chronic kidney disease, diabetic eye disease, and an elevated risk of heart disease and stroke. Individuals with prediabetes had a higher likelihood of developing diabetes compared to those with normal blood sugar levels.

The current analysis identified prediabetes using FBG and HbA1c, following the American Diabetes Association (ADA) (American Diabetes Association Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes 2020). [8] Individuals who are at a heightened risk of developing diabetes in the future can be diagnosed through the presence of abnormally low blood glucose levels (IFG: 100-125 mg/dL).

New recommendations have suggested using HbA1c to identify those who are at risk of developing advanced prediabetes. [9] In a study involving individuals with a family history of diabetes, multiple factors were found to be long-term predictors of impaired fasting glucose (IFG). However, only a few factors were identified as long-term predictors for prediabetes, which include age, gender, fasting blood glucose levels, triglycerides, and uric acid levels.

In the present study, the body mass index (BMI) was considerably higher in individuals with prediabetes compared to those with normal blood sugar levels (normoglycemia). These results align with recent findings that suggested the increased risk of overweight/obesity in diabetes. [] Obesity can lead to the development of insulin resistance, which in turn impairs glucose levels and ultimately leads to pre-diabetes.

Regarding this matter, Neeland and colleagues discovered that there is a separate connection between excess visceral fat, insulin resistance, and the advancement of prediabetes in obese adult patients. [11] Furthermore, there is a positive correlation between a greater body mass index (BMI) and an increased prevalence of pre-diabetes in adults. [12,13,14]

In addition to BMI, those with prediabetes exhibited a greater waist circumference compared to those with normoglycemia. This suggests that both BMI and waist circumference serve as reliable indicators for predicting prediabetes. [15,16] Some studies have found a correlation between abnormal liver function tests and a higher likelihood of acquiring prediabetes. [17,18]

ALT and ALP were found to be increased in prediabetics during the ongoing inquiry. ROC

curve analysis further validated the importance of these liver enzymes in elevating the likelihood of developing prediabetes. Prior research has indicated that ALT and ALP may play a role in predicting prediabetes. Research has established a correlation between prediabetes and elevated levels of ALT and ALP. These findings indicate that both enzymes operate as separate risk factors for the development of diabetes, regardless of gender.

Elevated ALT levels have been associated with reduced insulin sensitivity in the liver, as well as increased risk of obesity, insulin resistance, and probable development of diabetes. Moreover, elevated levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) are considered a contributing factor in the development of prediabetes, suggesting that the liver plays a role in the disease's progression.

Furthermore, research has demonstrated that serum ALT levels serve as a reliable indicator of prediabetes in the general population, even in those without any recognised risk factors for the condition. [19] Hatano and colleagues conducted ROC curve analysis and determined that the area under the curve (AUC) for ALT in prediabetes was assessed to be 0.71. This study's results agreed with previous research findings, which reported an AUC of 0.891 for ALT and was published earlier this year. [20,21]

Occasionally, the elevation of liver enzymes might be attributed to fat accumulation in the liver caused by insulin resistance syndrome, which has been recognised as a symptom. [22,23] Another potential pathophysiological explanation has been proposed, suggesting that high liver enzymes may indicate an inflammatory condition.

This condition is associated with impaired insulin signalling both in the liver and throughout the body. Prediabetes has been associated with persistent changes in transaminases and impaired hepatic function in this particular situation. Regular monitoring of liver parameters in high-risk patients for diabetes can prevent future hepatic complications resulting from insulin resistance. [9,24]

This study demonstrates that ALT, ALP, and obesity serve as reliable indicators of prediabetes. However, additional investigation is required to comprehend the underlying mechanism via which the association between liver function enzymes and the susceptibility to diabetes is initially established.

Conclusion

This study highlights the potential role of liver function tests, particularly ALT, ALP, and obesity, in the early diagnosis of prediabetes, offering a simple and cost-effective screening tool in clinical practice. Further research is needed to validate

these findings in larger, more diverse populations and to explore the underlying mechanisms linking liver function to glucose metabolism.

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